

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL FACTORS AND CONDITIONS OF CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT EFFECTIVENESS**Omadbek Olimjonov Odiljon ugli**

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Abstract. This article describes in detail the psychological and pedagogical factors and conditions of classroom management, methods of classroom management, the work of the class teacher with school community organizations, the important requirements for the class teacher, the main tasks of classroom management in the school charter.

Keywords: classroom management effectiveness, classroom leadership, personal development, school charter, learning activities.

ПСИХОЛОГО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ФАКТОРЫ И УСЛОВИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ КЛАССНОГО РУКОВОДСТВА

Аннотация. В данной статье подробно описаны психолого-педагогические факторы и условия классного руководства, методы классного руководства, работа классного руководителя с общественными организациями школы, важные требования к классному руководителю, основные задачи классного руководства в школьном уставе.

Ключевые слова: эффективность управления классом, лидерство в классе, личностное развитие, устав школы, учебная деятельность.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of personal education is to create sufficient pedagogical conditions for students to fully demonstrate their abilities. In this regard, the school, in collaboration with the teaching staff and the student body, takes an individual approach to the organization of educational work, taking into account the specific characteristics of each student.

A class teacher is a teacher who leads a team of students of the same level, age, and education. The main goal of the class teacher is to be able to understand each other with the student and the class teacher in the process of educating the students properly, and to be more attentive to the students by the class teacher.

Establishing relationships with students and rebuilding them as students grow and develop are also important for the class teacher. The class teacher keeps records of its work and submits them to the school administration.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The school educates students through the work of the class teacher, including activities, poetry readings, various evenings, meetings, contests, and other games. As a result, students develop thinking skills.

The class teacher works in partnership with the school administration and the community, as well as parents. The school administration should always support the class leader and his work. Because the class teacher knows his students well, he takes into account what is needed to teach them. The work of the class teacher is supervised by the Deputy Director for Spirituality and Enlightenment.

The class teacher's work plan is developed and supervised by the school principal and deputy principal. They acquire knowledge, skills and competencies in their educational activities.

The teacher often works alone with the class and as an educator. Teachers are distinguished by great love and care for children. These are being done with great demand.

RESULTS

Conducts health promotion activities for students and teaches them to work physically and mentally. The role of the class leader is important in organizing the class and organizing the class meeting. To hold a class meeting, the team first gathers.

The class leader discusses many issues at the meeting. At the class meeting, 3-4 issues are discussed and the problematic aspects are analyzed and resolved.

The class leader should encourage the best students in the class or community during the meeting. Children are friendly to each other. Encourage them to read each other well.

Children who read poorly read well, and so do children. In addition, the class leader should create a classroom library for student development. Students can read books in this library during extracurricular activities or when they are free after class.

The school charter defines the main responsibilities of the class teacher. The class leader liaises with all teachers and conducts educational work with his or her class.

Achieve uniformity of pedagogical requirements imposed on students by teachers. Parents, full-time educators are in constant contact with the community. Organizes with help when needed.

Keeps class records and submits them to the school administration. Conducts health promotion activities for teachers and trains them to work. The peculiarity of the work of the class leader is that he forms a group of students, not a group of ordinary children.

DISCUSSION

One of the most important requirements for a class leader is that the class leader knows his or her job well. He must have mastered his style. It needs to be organized properly and spent with children in an understandable, fun and responsible way.

Students not only appreciate the teacher's ability to communicate their knowledge to children, but also his or her interest and dedication to science. A modern teacher, especially a class teacher, should not only know our national values, but also be a strong advocate for them in the wider parent community, in the classroom.

One of the main tasks of a class teacher is to educate our future generation in a correct and humane spirit. In the process of education, the teacher and the class teacher should understand each other, and the class teacher should pay more attention to the teachers.

The main task of students is to read. Therefore, the class teacher first determines how the children will react to school, how they will behave, whether or not they will do their homework diligently, and finally, most importantly, what their learning goals will be. These goals are considered to have social significance or not.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the class teacher works with the school administration and the community.

The school administration should support the class leader and his or her work. Because the class teacher knows his teachers well and takes into account what he needs to do to educate them.

Acquire knowledge, skills and competencies in their learning activities. The teacher works alone with the class and often as an educator. The attitude of teachers towards children is characterized by great kindness and care. This is done with demand. Establishing the right relationship with teachers and rebuilding them as students grow and develop are also important for the class teacher.

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